

Probing Singlet Vector-Like Top Quarks in the Hadronic tZ ($Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$) Channel at the HL-LHC using Machine and Deep Learning Architectures

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Abstract

In this work, we study the single production of a vector-like singlet top partner T at the 14 TeV HL-LHC in the channel $pp \rightarrow Tj$ with $T \rightarrow tZ$, $t \rightarrow bW \rightarrow bj\bar{j}$, and $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$. Signal and background samples are generated with MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO v3.5.11, showered with PYTHIA 8, and passed through DELPHES. The dominant backgrounds are $t\bar{t}$, tZj , $ZZj\bar{j}$, and $WZj\bar{j}$ (including charge conjugates). A hadronic pre-selection ($N_j \geq 3$, $N_b \geq 1$, $N_\ell = 0$) is imposed as trigger, followed by optimized kinematic cuts. We perform multivariate classification with Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) and a Graph Neural Network (GNN) based on jet-level features. Sensitivities at 3000 fb^{-1} are quoted using the Asimov significance, $S/\sqrt{S+B}$, and an Asimov variant with a 20% background systematic. The model parameters g^* and R_L are defined in Sec. II, and a single global working point is used to avoid per-mass tuning bias. In the (g^*, m_T) scan we present 2σ exclusion and 5σ discovery contours for $R_L = 0$ and $R_L = 0.5$. For $R_L = 0$, 2σ exclusion corresponds to $g^* \in [0.17, 0.49]$ (0.16, 0.43) over $m_T \in [1.8, 2.7]$ TeV, while 5σ discovery corresponds to $g^* \in [0.27, 0.44]$ (0.26, 0.40) over $m_T \in [1.8, 2.2]$ TeV for XGBoost and GNN respectively. For $R_L = 0.5$, the 2σ reach is $g^* \in [0.21, 0.48]$ (0.20, 0.43) over $m_T \in [1.8, 2.5]$ TeV, and the 5σ reach is $g^* \in [0.33, 0.43]$ (0.31, 0.49) over $m_T \in [1.8, 2.2]$ TeV, with the GNN yielding slightly stronger and smoother limits across the scan.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Standard Model of Particle Physics is an epitome of mankind’s genius, as it has passed every precision test to date. However, it leaves open basic questions about electroweak naturalness, flavor, and the structure of physics at the TeV scale. A broad class of extensions predicts vector-like quarks (VLQs), heavy color-triplet fermions with identical left- and right-handed gauge quantum numbers [1–3]. Such states arise naturally in composite Higgs models, warped extra dimensions (Randall–Sundrum), and little Higgs theories, where gauge-invariant mass terms and mixing with SM quarks help regulate Higgs-sector radiative corrections [1, 3–6].

For a singlet top partner T , the dominant decay channels are $T \rightarrow bW$, $T \rightarrow tZ$, and $T \rightarrow tH$, with asymptotic branching ratios dictated by Goldstone equivalence at high mass [1, 3]. At the LHC, pair production is QCD-driven and model-independent but rapidly loses phase space at multi-TeV masses. Single production, while model-dependent, becomes increasingly important and is directly sensitive to the effective mixing coupling that controls the T –SM interaction strength. This makes single production the appropriate probe for the heavy-mass regime, especially at the HL-LHC.

ATLAS and CMS searches for singly produced T quarks in tZ and tH final states already push singlet- T limits into the TeV range [7–9]. The HL-LHC target luminosity of $\sim 3000 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ will extend this reach, but only if complex hadronic backgrounds are controlled [10]. This is particularly challenging when boosted hadronic decays overlap with QCD radiation and electroweak jet activity.

We therefore focus on the single-production topology $pp \rightarrow Tj$ with $T \rightarrow tZ$, $t \rightarrow bW \rightarrow bj\bar{j}$, and $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$. The hadronic top decay provides a large branching fraction, while the invisible Z yields a strong missing-energy handle. The price is a fully hadronic final state with substantial background from $t\bar{t}$, tZj , $ZZjj$, and $WZjj$ (including charge-conjugate modes), which populate similar regions of phase space. Heavy- T kinematics induce correlated structures in jet momenta, angular separations, and event-level variables, motivating multivariate methods that can exploit these correlations beyond a cut-based approach.

Simulation samples are generated with MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO v3.5.11 and processed with PYTHIA8 and DELPHES [11–13]. After a hadronic preselection ($N_j \geq 3$, $N_b \geq 1$, $N_\ell = 0$) and optimized kinematic cuts, we classify events with XGBoost [14] and a Graph Neural Network (GNN) that models jets as nodes with relational edges [15]. This enables a direct, controlled comparison of tree-based and graph-based classifiers in a high-background, hadronic environment.

Compared to the recent cut-based and BDT-style studies of the hadronic tZ channel [16], the

novelty of this work is threefold: (i) we provide a head-to-head comparison of XGBoost and a Graph Neural Network within the same 5FS, detector-level setup; (ii) we adopt a single global working point across the mass scan to avoid per-mass tuning partiality; and (iii) we translate the ML outputs into coupled (g^*, m_T) reach contours with a uniform treatment of weights and systematics. This isolates the gain from relational learning in a realistic hadronic environment and quantifies its impact on exclusion and discovery reach.

We scan a simplified singlet- T parameter space in (m_T, g^*, R_L) , presenting results for $R_L = 0$ and $R_L = 0.5$ as benchmark mixing scenarios. Exclusion (2σ) and discovery (5σ) contours are derived at 3000 fb^{-1} using a single global threshold. The GNN yields a modest but consistent improvement in sensitivity, producing smoother and slightly stronger contours across the whole scan.

The paper is organized as follows. Sec. II summarizes the singlet- T model and parameter definitions. Sec. III details event generation, detector simulation, and selection cuts. Sec. IV presents the multivariate analysis, including model architectures and feature sets. Sec. V reports the classifier performance and the resulting reach in (g^*, m_T) . Sec. VI concludes with a summary and outlook.

II. THE SINGLET VECTOR-LIKE TOP-QUARK MODEL

We summarize the simplified singlet- T framework used in the analysis and fix our notation. The setup follows standard VLQ effective descriptions and the parameterization commonly adopted in recent $T \rightarrow tZ$ studies [1–3, 16].

A. Field Content, Couplings, and Parameterization

We consider a single vector-like top partner T with electric charge $+2/3$, transforming as an $SU(2)_L$ singlet. The interactions relevant for single production and decay are written in an effective form controlled by an overall coupling strength g^* and a mixing parameter R_L that fixes the relative coupling to first- and third-generation quarks. It is convenient to define

$$c_1 \equiv \sqrt{\frac{R_L}{1+R_L}}, \quad c_3 \equiv \sqrt{\frac{1}{1+R_L}}. \quad (1)$$

Here $R_L = 0$ corresponds to pure third-generation coupling, while $R_L \rightarrow \infty$ gives pure first-generation coupling. In terms of $c_{1,3}$, the interaction Lagrangian can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_T = & \frac{g g^*}{2\sqrt{2}} \left(c_1 \bar{T}_L \gamma^\mu W_\mu^+ d_L + c_3 \bar{T}_L \gamma^\mu W_\mu^+ b_L \right) + \frac{g g^*}{4c_W} \left(c_1 \bar{T}_L \gamma^\mu Z_\mu u_L + c_3 \bar{T}_L \gamma^\mu Z_\mu t_L \right) \\ & - \frac{g g^*}{2m_W} \left(c_1 \bar{T}_R H u_L + c_3 \bar{T}_R H t_L \right) + \text{h.c.} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where g is the $SU(2)_L$ gauge coupling, $c_W \equiv \cos \theta_W$, and H is the SM Higgs doublet. The effective coupling g^* sets the overall single-production strength, while R_L encodes the relative mixing with first- and third-generation quarks. This parametrization is standard in VLQ phenomenology and enables a direct scan in (m_T, g^*, R_L) without committing to a specific UV completion [1, 16].

B. Partial Widths, Branching Ratios, and Limiting Behavior

The dominant decay modes of a singlet T are

$$T \rightarrow bW, \quad T \rightarrow tZ, \quad T \rightarrow tH, \quad (3)$$

with additional channels into first-generation quarks when $R_L \neq 0$. For a generic decay $T \rightarrow Vq$ ($V = W, Z$) the partial width can be written as

$$\Gamma(T \rightarrow Vq) = \frac{\kappa_V^2 m_T^3}{32\pi m_V^2} \lambda^{1/2}(1, x_V, x_q) \left[(1 - x_q)^2 + (1 + x_q - 2x_V)x_V \right], \quad (4)$$

where $x_i = m_i^2/m_T^2$, $\lambda(a, b, c) = a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - 2ab - 2ac - 2bc$ is the Källén function, and κ_V encodes the relevant coupling factor from Eq. (2). For the scalar decay $T \rightarrow Hq$ one finds

$$\Gamma(T \rightarrow Hq) = \frac{\kappa_H^2 m_T^3}{32\pi m_W^2} \lambda^{1/2}(1, x_H, x_q) (1 + x_q - x_H), \quad (5)$$

with κ_H fixed by the Yukawa-like term in Eq. (2). In the heavy-mass limit $m_T \gg m_t, m_W, m_Z, m_H$, these expressions reduce to the familiar approximate forms

$$\Gamma(T \rightarrow Wd_i) \simeq \frac{c_i^2 (gg^*)^2}{64\pi} \frac{m_T^3}{m_W^2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\Gamma(T \rightarrow Zu_i) \simeq \frac{c_i^2 (gg^*)^2}{128\pi} \frac{m_T^3}{m_W^2} \frac{1}{c_W^2}, \quad (7)$$

$$\Gamma(T \rightarrow Hu_i) \simeq \frac{c_i^2 (gg^*)^2}{128\pi} \frac{m_T^3}{m_W^2}, \quad (8)$$

where $i = 1, 3$ denotes the generation index and $c_i = (c_1, c_3)$. The total width is obtained by summing over all accessible modes and generations, and the branching ratio for the signal channel is

$$\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ) = \frac{\Gamma(T \rightarrow tZ)}{\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}. \quad (9)$$

FIG. 1: Branching ratio $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$ in the (R_L, m_T) plane.

In the large- m_T limit the overall factor $(gg^*)^2$ cancels in ratios, so $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$ depends primarily on R_L and only weakly on m_T through phase space. This motivates the (R_L, m_T) branching-ratio map shown in Fig. 1, which summarizes how the tZ mode evolves across the scan range.

For $R_L = 0$, couplings are purely to the third generation and $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$ is maximal within the singlet framework. As R_L increases, the coupling is shared with the first generation, reducing $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$ while opening light-quark modes. The contour map therefore provides a direct link between the model parameter R_L and the observable tZ signal fraction used in the analysis.

C. Benchmark Choices

Throughout the analysis we present results for two benchmark mixing scenarios, $R_L = 0$ (pure third-generation coupling) and $R_L = 0.5$ (mixed coupling). The effective coupling g^* is scanned over the range $[0.1, 0.5]$, and the mass m_T is scanned over the range relevant to the HL-LHC reach in this channel. These choices enable a direct comparison of exclusion and discovery contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane.

We adopt the five-flavor scheme (5FS), in which the b quark is treated as a parton in the proton. This is standard for single production of heavy top partners and enhances the relevance of the Tj topology at large masses. Details of event generation, PDF choice, and matching are given in

Sec. III.

For single production, the dependence on the effective coupling is approximately quadratic: in the narrow-width regime, the inclusive cross section scales as

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow Tj) \propto (g^*)^2 \times f(m_T, R_L), \quad (10)$$

where $f(m_T, R_L)$ encodes phase-space suppression and the parton-level mixing structure. This scaling motivates the g^* scan and allows a transparent interpretation of the reach contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane.

III. EVENT SELECTIONS AND KINEMATICS DISTRIBUTIONS

Signal and background samples are generated at leading-order (LO) with MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO v3.5.11 [11]. The signal process is

$$pp \rightarrow Tj, \quad T \rightarrow tZ, \quad t \rightarrow bW \rightarrow bj\bar{j}, \quad Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}, \quad (11)$$

including the charge-conjugate mode $pp \rightarrow \bar{T}j$. The dominant SM backgrounds are $t\bar{t}$, tZj , $ZZjj$, and $WZjj$ (including charge-conjugate channels). The coupling parameters g^* and R_L enter only the signal model, where the backgrounds are generated with SM couplings. Signal samples in the mass scan are generated at fixed $g^* = 0.4$ and $R_L = 0.5$, and the reach in (g^*, R_L) is obtained by rescaling using the $(g^*)^2$ dependence and the branching-ratio map discussed in Sec. II. The analysis is performed in the five-flavor scheme (5FS), where the b quark is treated as a proton parton, as is standard for single production of heavy top partners.

Parton-level generation cuts are imposed to stabilize the matrix-element integration and reflect basic detector acceptance:

$$\begin{aligned} p_T(j), p_T(b), p_T(\ell) &> 25 \text{ GeV}, \\ |\eta(j)| < 5.0, \quad |\eta(b)| < 5.0, \quad |\eta(\ell)| < 2.5, \\ \Delta R(x, y) &> 0.4 \quad \text{for all particle pairs.} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

We use the LHAPDF6 interface with set ID 331100 [17]. Electroweak input parameters are fixed to $m_t = 172.52$ GeV, $m_H = 125.11$ GeV, $m_Z = 91.1876$ GeV, $m_W = 80.379$ GeV, $\alpha_s(m_Z) = 0.118$, $1/\alpha(m_Z) = 132.185$, and $G_F = 1.66 \times 10^{-5}$ GeV⁻².

Parton showering and hadronization are performed with PYTHIA8 [12]. Detector effects are simulated using DELPHES [13] with a CMS-style card tuned to the analysis requirements, that provides the consistent reconstruction of jets, b -tags, and missing transverse momentum. No additional

multi-jet merging is applied in the signal samples. The extra jet is generated at matrix-element level in $pp \rightarrow Tj$.

After detector simulation, events must satisfy a hadronic preselection:

$$N_j \geq 3, \quad N_b \geq 1, \quad N_\ell = 0. \quad (13)$$

Additional optimized cuts are then applied to suppress backgrounds while retaining signal efficiency in the boosted regime. The baseline selections (as implemented in the analysis macro) are:

$$\begin{aligned} p_T(b_1) &> 60 \text{ GeV}, & p_T(j_1) &> 120 \text{ GeV}, \\ \Delta R(j_1, j_2) &< 3.0, & \Delta R(j_1, j_3) &< 3.5, \\ E_T^{\text{miss}} &> 160 \text{ GeV}, \\ 40 \text{ GeV} &< m_{jj} < 140 \text{ GeV}, & \chi_t^2 &< 60, \\ 80 \text{ GeV} &< m_{bjj} < 320 \text{ GeV}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

These requirements target the reconstructed hadronic top and W candidates while maintaining sensitivity to heavy- T kinematics. The full list of observables used in the multivariate step is described in Sec. IV.

To illustrate the selection criteria, Table II summarizes the cutflow for two representative signal benchmarks, $m_T = 1800$ and 2000 GeV, together with the dominant backgrounds. The reported values are the effective cross sections after each cut, including the K -factor normalization used in this work. We rescale the leading-order cross sections by process-dependent K factors. In accordance with Ref. [16], which uses the same 14 TeV setup and 5FS treatment, we use $K = 1.27$ for $ZZjj$, $K = 1.14$ for $WZjj$, and $K = 1.10$ for tZj . The $t\bar{t}$ background is normalized to the NNLO QCD prediction [18], and for the signal we adopt a conservative K factor of 0.95 as in Ref. [19]. These K factors are taken as fixed normalization inputs across the scan to facilitate direct comparison with prior studies. All quoted sensitivities use these normalized cross sections with an integrated luminosity of 3000 fb^{-1} . Other SM processes are sub-leading after the hadronic preselection and optimized cuts and are therefore neglected in the baseline analysis.

TABLE I: Standard Model backgrounds with decay modes, and LO cross sections (fb).

Production process	Decay mode	Cross section (fb)
$pp \rightarrow t\bar{t}$	$t \rightarrow jjb, \bar{t} \rightarrow \ell^- \bar{\nu}_\ell \bar{b}$	210620
$pp \rightarrow tZj$	$t \rightarrow jjb, Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$	121.52
$pp \rightarrow ZZjj$	$Z \rightarrow jj, Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$	1161.9
$pp \rightarrow W^\pm Zjj$	$W^\pm \rightarrow jj, Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$	2908.3

TABLE II: Cutflow for the signal benchmarks (T1800, T2000) and backgrounds at 14 TeV. Effective cross sections are in fb.

Cuts	Signal (fb)	Backgrounds (fb)			
	T1800(T2000)	tt	tZj	$ZZjj$	$WZjj$
σ (Before cut)	9.832(6.679)	340362.082	44.022	216.660	548.331
Trigger	5.089(3.246)	140370.768	23.131	50.246	69.797
$p_T[b_1] > 60$ GeV	4.489(2.846)	97818.020	14.093	27.919	39.759
$p_T[j_1] > 120$ GeV	4.438(2.818)	39383.296	6.094	13.426	23.778
$\Delta R[j_1, j_2] < 3.0$	2.741(1.707)	22951.977	2.243	8.074	13.971
$\Delta R[j_1, j_3] < 3.5$	1.598(0.982)	20713.075	1.818	7.287	12.373
$E_T^{\text{miss}} > 160$ GeV	1.590(0.978)	3360.054	0.750	3.135	5.769
N(light jets) ≥ 2	1.546(0.951)	3055.771	0.675	2.670	5.497
$40 < m_{jj} < 140$ GeV	0.890(0.542)	2415.890	0.401	1.582	3.249
$\chi_{\text{top}}^2 < 60$	0.639(0.371)	2332.842	0.386	1.360	2.686
$80 < m_{bjj} < 320$ GeV	0.585(0.336)	2282.468	0.379	1.288	2.526

FIG. 2: Representative LO t -channel diagram for single production $pp \rightarrow Tj$ in the 5FS with $T \rightarrow tZ$, $t \rightarrow bW \rightarrow bj\bar{j}$, and $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$.

IV. THE MACHINE AND DEEP LEARNING METHODS FOR THE CLASSIFICATION

The fully hadronic tZ topology with large missing transverse momentum exhibits correlated kinematic and angular structure that is difficult to capture with cut-based selections alone. To maximize signal sensitivity while controlling the dominant backgrounds, we employ multivariate classifiers that learn non-linear decision boundaries in a high-dimensional feature space. We use two sophisticated approaches of extreme gradient-boosted decision trees (XGBoost), which are robust for tabular inputs and widely used in HEP, and a graph neural network (GNN), which represents the event as a jet graph and encodes inter-object relations directly. This pairing provides a strong baseline and a physics-motivated extension beyond traditional methods.

For XGBoost we use the standard regularized boosting objective [14],

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_i \ell(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum_{k=1}^K \Omega(f_k), \quad \Omega(f_k) = \gamma T_k + \frac{\lambda}{2} \|w_k\|^2, \quad (15)$$

where ℓ is the logistic loss, f_k denotes a tree with T_k leaves and weights w_k , and γ, λ control model complexity. The model predicts a signal score $s(\mathbf{x}) \in [0, 1]$ from the feature vector \mathbf{x} and provides interpretable feature-importance measures. For the GNN, we construct an event graph in which jets are nodes and pairwise relations are encoded as edges, following standard particle-physics graph learning formulations [15]. A generic message-passing layer updates node embeddings as

$$h_v^{(l+1)} = \phi \left(h_v^{(l)}, \sum_{u \in \mathcal{N}(v)} \psi \left(h_v^{(l)}, h_u^{(l)}, e_{vu} \right) \right), \quad (16)$$

TABLE III: Feature sets used for XGBoost and GNN. Node features use the leading jets and the b jet, edge features encode pairwise separations, and global features summarize event-level energy flow.

Category	XGBoost features	GNN features
Global/event-level	$E_T^{\text{miss}}, S_T, H_T/(H_T + E_T^{\text{miss}}), m_T^T, E_T^{\text{miss}}, H_T, S_T, H_T/(H_T + E_T^{\text{miss}}), \Delta\phi(\vec{p}_T^{bjj}, \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}})$	$m_T^T, \Delta\phi(\vec{p}_T^{bjj}, \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}})$
Reconstruction/topology	$m_{bjj}, p_T(j_1)$	—
Angular structure	$\Delta R(j_1, j_2), \Delta R(j_1, j_3), \Delta R(b, j_1)$	$\Delta R(j_1, j_2), \Delta R(j_1, j_3), \Delta R(j_2, j_3), \Delta R(b, j_1), \Delta R(b, j_2)$
Node features	—	(p_T, η, ϕ, m) for j_1, j_2, j_3, b_1

followed by a graph-level readout $h_G = \text{READOUT}(\{h_v\})$ and a final classification head. This architecture is well-suited to hadronic final states where the event topology and inter-jet correlations carry discriminating information beyond single-object kinematics.

Table III summarizes the input variables used for each classifier. For XGBoost we use a compact set of high-level observables that capture energy scales, angular structure, and reconstructed top-like kinematics. For the GNN, node features correspond to per-jet kinematics, edge features encode angular separations, and global features summarize event-level energy flow. The reconstructed hadronic top candidate is built by combining the leading b -tagged jet with the two highest- p_T light jets. The invariant mass m_{bjj} and the corresponding top- χ^2 are computed from this triplet and used in the cut selection; m_{bjj} also enters the ML feature set. We define H_T as the scalar sum of jet transverse momenta and $S_T \equiv H_T + E_T^{\text{miss}}$. Because the Z decays invisibly, no Z mass reconstruction is performed; instead, we use E_T^{miss} , the transverse-mass proxy m_T^T built from the bjj system and E_T^{miss} , and $\Delta\phi(\vec{p}_T^{bjj}, \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}})$ to capture the T -scale kinematics. We further define $H_T^{\text{frac}} \equiv H_T/(H_T + E_T^{\text{miss}})$, which quantifies the balance between visible hadronic activity and missing energy. This ratio compresses the event-scale information into a dimensionless balance variable and helps separate signal, which tends to have larger E_T^{miss} , from backgrounds dominated by visible hadronic activity.

Events are split into training, validation, and test samples. To avoid domination by the large background yield, we rebalance weights only during training so that the total weighted signal and background contributions are comparable. Nevertheless, all physics results (yields and significances) are computed using the original event weights. Overtraining is monitored using Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) tests on signal and background score distributions for training vs. test

samples (Table V) [20]. Final model selection is based on validation performance and stable KS p -values after manual hyperparameter tuning for both XGBoost and GNN. Hyperparameters were tuned on the validation set to achieve stable AUC and KS behavior across iterations.

The key hyperparameters used in the final models are summarized in Table IV. We report the most relevant settings for reproducibility, whereas the remaining values are kept at library defaults.

TABLE IV: Key hyperparameters used for the XGBoost and GNN models.

Model	Hyperparameter	Value
XGBoost	$n_{\text{estimators}}$, max depth, η	350, 3, 0.05
XGBoost	subsample, colsample_bytree	0.7, 0.7
XGBoost	γ , min child_weight	0.2, 2.0
XGBoost	λ , α	1.0, 0.0
GNN	Layers, hidden size, activation	2, 64, ReLU
GNN	Dropout, optimizer	0.2, Adam
GNN	Learning rate, weight decay	10^{-3} , 10^{-4}
GNN	Epochs, batch size	50, 512

Classifier performance is quantified using ROC curves and AUC. The output score $s(\mathbf{x})$ is used as a discriminant. For a chosen threshold $s > s_0$ we compute the weighted signal and background yields by

$$S(s_0) = \sum_{i \in \text{sig}} w_i \Theta(s_i - s_0), \quad B(s_0) = \sum_{i \in \text{bkg}} w_i \Theta(s_i - s_0), \quad (17)$$

where w_i are the event weights and Θ is the Heaviside step function. We report the Asimov significance [20],

$$Z_A = \sqrt{2 \left[(S + B) \ln \left(1 + \frac{S}{B} \right) - S \right]}, \quad (18)$$

the simple estimator

$$Z_{S/\sqrt{S+B}} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{S+B}}, \quad (19)$$

and an Asimov variant including a 20% background systematic uncertainty $\sigma_B = 0.2B$,

$$Z_{A, \sigma_B} = \sqrt{2 \left[(S + B) \ln \left(\frac{(S + B)(B + \sigma_B^2)}{B^2 + (S + B)\sigma_B^2} \right) - \frac{B^2}{\sigma_B^2} \ln \left(1 + \frac{\sigma_B^2 S}{B(B + \sigma_B^2)} \right) \right]}. \quad (20)$$

A single global working point is defined from the combined validation sample and applied to all mass points. The resulting distributions, ROC curves, and feature importance rankings are presented in Sec. V together with the exclusion and discovery contours.

FIG. 3: Input variable distributions for XGBoost at the benchmark mass $m_T = 2000$ GeV.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table II (Sec. III) shows the cutflow for two representative benchmarks, $m_T = 1800$ and 2000 GeV, together with the dominant backgrounds. The pattern follows the expected physics of the hadronic tZ topology. The E_T^{miss} requirement targets the invisible $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$ decay, while the hard recoil and collimated jets from a boosted top motivate the $p_T(j_1)$ and ΔR selections. The m_{jj} window and χ_t^2 enforce consistency with a hadronic $W \rightarrow jj$ and $t \rightarrow bj\bar{j}$ reconstruction. Quantitatively (using the summed background columns), the trigger already removes $\sim 59\%$ of the background while keeping $\sim 49\text{--}52\%$ of the signal. The $p_T(j_1)$ cut yields a further $\sim 60\%$ background reduction with $\sim 99\%$ signal retention, and the E_T^{miss} cut is the single most powerful step, suppressing backgrounds by $\sim 84\%$ while retaining $\gtrsim 99.5\%$ of the signal. The two ΔR cuts reduce the background by $\sim 42\%$ and $\sim 10\%$ per step with $\sim 58\text{--}62\%$ signal retention, and the m_{jj} window removes another $\sim 21\%$ of background at $\sim 57\%$ signal efficiency. The final top-consistency cuts (χ_t^2 and the $m_{bj\bar{j}}$ window) are milder ($\sim 3\%$ and $\sim 2\%$ background reduction) but improve

FIG. 4: Input variable distributions for GNN at the benchmark mass $m_T = 2000$ GeV.

the kinematic fidelity of the reconstructed top.¹

Figure 5 compares the classifier score distributions, and Fig. 6 shows the ROC curves. Across the scan, the test AUC values for XGBoost lie in the range 0.976–0.983, while the GNN reaches 0.983–0.990, an average absolute gain of $\sim 7 \times 10^{-3}$ (about 0.7%). This improvement is expected as the GNN uses per-jet features and pairwise relations (e.g., ΔR structure and jet hierarchies), which are well matched to the boosted $t \rightarrow bj\bar{j}$ topology recoiling against invisible $Z \rightarrow \nu\bar{\nu}$. Whereas, XGBoost relies on engineered global observables that only partially encode combinatorial and relational information. Overtraining evaluation is carried out using KS tests on the test samples. The corresponding p -values fall in the ranges 0.121–0.834 (signal) and 0.098–0.443 (background) for XGBoost, and 0.316–0.875 (signal) and 0.820–0.968 (background) for the GNN (Table V). These values indicate a stable generalization and no significant overtraining. We note a mild non-monotonicity in the GNN AUC around $m_T = 2900$ GeV. This is consistent with limited statistics at the highest masses and the stochasticity of training. The overall trend remains stable and the global ranking of GNN vs. XGBoost is unchanged.

¹ All quoted reductions and efficiencies are step-wise (relative to the preceding cut) and are consistent between the $m_T = 1800$ and 2000 GeV benchmarks in Table II.

(a) XGBoost score distribution.

(b) GNN score distribution.

FIG. 5: Classifier score distributions for signal and background at the benchmark mass $m_T = 2000$ GeV for (a) XGBoost, and (b) GNN.

(a) XGBoost ROC curve.

(b) GNN ROC curve.

FIG. 6: ROC curves at $m_T = 2000$ GeV for (a) XGBoost and (b) GNN.

The classifier outputs are translated into physics reach using the significance measures defined in Sec. IV. The adopted global working points are derived from the combined validation samples, and the resulting thresholds are $s_0 = 0.99$ for both XGBoost and the GNN. Figure 8 shows the resulting Z score versus m_T . The XGBoost significance ranges are $Z_A = 0.174\text{--}3.355$, $S/\sqrt{S+B} = 0.174\text{--}3.298$, and $Z_{A,\sigma_B} = 0.0135\text{--}0.258$. The corresponding GNN ranges are $Z_A = 0.234\text{--}3.835$, $S/\sqrt{S+B} = 0.234\text{--}3.731$, and $Z_{A,\sigma_B} = 0.017\text{--}0.416$. As expected, sensitivity decreases with increasing m_T due to phase-space suppression and reduced signal yield.

TABLE V: KS test p -values (test sample) for XGBoost and GNN.

m_T [GeV]	XGBoost		GNN	
	$p_{\text{KS}}^{\text{sig}}$	$p_{\text{KS}}^{\text{bkg}}$	$p_{\text{KS}}^{\text{sig}}$	$p_{\text{KS}}^{\text{bkg}}$
1800	0.792	0.098	0.875	0.968
2000	0.348	0.247	0.316	0.938
2200	0.121	0.187	0.500	0.905
2500	0.834	0.162	0.761	0.931
2700	0.490	0.443	0.467	0.887
2900	0.288	0.384	0.839	0.874
3100	0.147	0.320	0.778	0.820

FIG. 7: Test AUC vs. m_T for XGBoost and GNN.

Figure 9 and Fig. 10 present the 2σ exclusion and 5σ discovery contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane for $R_L = 0$ and $R_L = 0.5$. The contours show the expected trade-off between coupling strength and mass reach. At the fixed g^* the reachable mass decreases with m_T due to phase-space suppression, while at fixed m_T larger g^* compensates the reduced rate. Comparing the two mixing scenarios, $R_L = 0.5$ yields broader exclusion and discovery coverage than $R_L = 0$. This is physically expected, although $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$ decreases with increasing R_L , the single-production rate is enhanced by the larger first-generation component, which benefits from higher light-quark parton luminosities. The

FIG. 8: Significance vs. m_T at the global threshold for (a) XGBoost and (b) GNN.

FIG. 9: Exclusion and discovery contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane for $R_L = 0.0$.

net effect is an overall gain in sensitivity for $R_L = 0.5$, especially at larger masses where production is the limiting factor. Across both scenarios, the GNN contours lie modestly outside the XGBoost contours, consistent with the improved classifier separation seen in the ROC and AUC comparisons. The corresponding g^* thresholds at each m_T are summarized in Table VI in Appendix A.

FIG. 10: Exclusion and discovery contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane for $R_L = 0.5$.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have presented a feasibility study of single production of a vector-like singlet top partner in the hadronic tZ channel at the 14 TeV HL-LHC. The analysis follows a consistent workflow: 5FS event generation, detector simulation, physics-motivated preselection, and multivariate classification. We evaluate both XGBoost and a GNN using a global working-point strategy which is essential for a uniform comparison across the scan, with global thresholds $s_0 = 0.99$ for both models calculated from independent validation samples.

Both classifiers generalize stably with no evidence of over-training. Across the complete scan, test AUC values lie in the ranges 0.976–0.983 (XGBoost) and 0.983–0.990 (GNN), corresponding to an average absolute gain of $\sim 7 \times 10^{-3}$ (about 0.7%) in AUC for the graph model. Using the classifier outputs to define signal regions, we derive 2σ exclusion and 5σ discovery contours in the (g^*, m_T) plane for $R_L = 0$ and $R_L = 0.5$. The statistical Asimov significance spans $Z_A = 0.174$ – 3.355 (XGBoost) and $Z_A = 0.234$ – 3.835 (GNN), with the same ordering for $S/\sqrt{S+B}$ and the 20% systematic variant. The $R_L = 0.5$ scenario exhibits broader coverage, driven by enhanced single-production rates from light-quark parton luminosities despite a reduced $\text{Br}(T \rightarrow tZ)$. These results provide a compact, ML-assisted projection of HL-LHC sensitivity for this channel.

Future refinements could include NLO-accurate signal and background modeling, a more de-

tailed treatment of detector-level systematics across phase space (JES/JER, b -tagging, and lepton misidentification), and complementary decay channels (e.g., $Z \rightarrow \ell\ell$) to strengthen high-mass reach. A combined multi-channel analysis with correlated systematics would provide a more comprehensive HL-LHC sensitivity assessment and a clearer path to experimental interpretation.

VII. STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

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Competing Interests

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

Appendix A: Parameter Space Scan Threshold Table

TABLE VI: g^* thresholds for 2σ exclusion and 5σ discovery at each m_T for $R_L = 0$ and $R_L = 0.5$. Entries marked “–” indicate that the threshold is not reached within the scanned g^* range.

R_L	m_T [GeV]	XGB $g_{2\sigma}^*$	XGB $g_{5\sigma}^*$	GNN $g_{2\sigma}^*$	GNN $g_{5\sigma}^*$
0.0	1800	0.17	0.27	0.16	0.26
0.0	2000	0.22	0.35	0.20	0.32
0.0	2200	0.28	0.44	0.26	0.40
0.0	2500	0.39	–	0.35	–
0.0	2700	0.49	–	0.43	–
0.0	2900	–	–	–	–
0.0	3100	–	–	–	–
0.5	1800	0.21	0.33	0.20	0.31
0.5	2000	0.27	0.43	0.25	0.39
0.5	2200	0.34	–	0.31	0.49
0.5	2500	0.48	–	0.43	–
0.5	2700	–	–	–	–
0.5	2900	–	–	–	–
0.5	3100	–	–	–	–

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